

Location

Berlin, Germany

Innovation

Building Inspection & Valuation
(AI-driven defect detection)

Partners

TU Berlin

DATA TYPES, TOOLS, REPOSITORIES, URLS

Data types

RGB images of masonry
surfaces, annotated crack masks

Tools

Python
Scikit-learn
TensorFlow/PyTorch
LabelMe

Methods

Random Forest
XGBoost
CNN
UNet

Repository/Platform

Local experimental datasets
Integration potential with CP-IM

SUMMARY OF SCOPE AND GOALS

This work develops and validates an AI-driven, non-destructive methodology for assessing the structural condition of masonry elements. It combines computer vision techniques with machine learning and deep learning models to automatically detect, classify, and segment cracks in masonry surfaces.

The approach aims to support scalable, data-driven inspection workflows that improve accuracy, reduce manual effort, and enable informed decision-making in circular construction contexts.

KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

- › Crack detection accuracy: up to 89% (CNN models)
- › Segmentation quality: IoU = 0.81, Dice coefficient = 0.89 (UNet)
- › Automation level: significant reduction in manual inspection effort
- › Scalability: validated on real-world masonry datasets

IMPACT

HIGH

Techno-Economic
Impact

MEDIUM-HIGH

Societal Impact

HIGH

Scientific Impact

IMAGES

Figure 1. An overview of a convolutional neural network (CNN) architecture and the training process

Figure 2. Data collection process

CONTACTS

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